

A Generalization of Euler's Reflection Principle

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May 2026

Abstract

Continuous sums and products in the sense of Müller and Schleicher provide a framework that extends the usual notion of summation and product to real or even complex indexes. From this perspective, several special functions, including the Gamma, Barnes G , q -Gamma, and Hurwitz zeta functions, can be viewed as interpolated finite sums and products. In this article, we study reflection and multiplication phenomena in this general setting. For a class of functions that we call reflective, we prove that the reflected continuous product is divided into a principal factor and a 1-periodic correction, whose logarithm admits a computable Fourier expansion. When f has a polynomial zero at the origin, the principal factor becomes trigonometric, yielding an Euler-type reflection formula, which recovers Euler's reflection formula as a limiting case. We also prove a Gauss-type multiplication theorem in the same framework. Finally, we apply the reflection theorem to the q -Gamma function, obtaining the exact Fourier expansion for its reflection, together with other new identities.

1 Introduction

1.1 Fractional sums and special functions

Fractional sums and products provide a way to interpolate finite summation and product operators beyond integer indices. In a dedicated section, we will discuss the relationship between this framework and many fundamental special functions. In this sense, understanding symmetries in continuous products and summations is particularly relevant for special functions, where functional equations, reflection formulas, multiplication formulas, and periodicity play a central role.

1.2 Main Results

Euler's reflection formula for the Gamma function suggests the following question: is the link between Gamma and trigonometric functions a special feature, or does it arise from a more general mechanism for continuous products? The

purpose of this paper is to prove that such a mechanism exists. We study reflected continuous products of the form

$$\Pi_f(x) := \prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k),$$

where the products are understood in the sense of Müller-Schleicher. We define a class of functions that we call *reflective*, and we prove that

$$\Pi_f(x) = \frac{f(x)}{f(0)} H_f(x),$$

where H_f is a 1-periodic factor. Moreover, $\ln H_f$ admits the Fourier representation

$$\ln H_f(x) = \sum_{k \geq 1} A_k^f (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1), \quad A_k^f = \frac{2}{\pi k} \int_0^\infty (\ln f)'(t) \sin(2\pi kt) dt.$$

The coefficients satisfy the bound

$$|A_k^f| \leq \frac{\|(\ln f)''\|_{L^1(0,\infty)}}{\pi^2 k^2},$$

hence, the reflected product splits into a principal part and a controlled periodic correction.

The second main result concerns functions with a polynomial zero at the origin. Suppose that $f(x) = 0$ only at $x = 0$, and that for some $r \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\lambda > 0$,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x)}{x^r} = \lambda.$$

If the auxiliary function

$$h(x) = \begin{cases} f(x)/x^r, & x \neq 0, \\ \lambda, & x = 0 \end{cases}$$

belongs to the previous reflective class, then

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \frac{\pi^r f(x)}{\lambda \sin^r(\pi x)} H_h(x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}.$$

This gives an Euler-type reflection formula for a general class of continuous products. In particular, the trigonometric factor comes from the polynomial zero of f at the origin, while H_h measures the remaining periodic correction.

We also prove a Gauss-type multiplication theorem. If f is Eulerian reflective, then for any integer $n \geq 2$,

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{-j/n} f(k) = n^{-r/2} \left(\frac{(2\pi)^r}{\lambda} \right)^{(n-1)/2} \exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{\substack{k \geq 1 \\ n|k}} A_k^h \right).$$

Several identities are obtained as special cases. For $f(x) = x^2 + a$, $a > 0$, we find a reflection formula whose limit $a \rightarrow 0^+$ recovers the square of Euler's reflection formula independently. Moreover, we partially extend our result; thus, we apply it to the q-Gamma function, obtaining as a corollary:

$$\Gamma_q(1+x)\Gamma_q(1-x) = \frac{\pi(q^{|x|}-1)}{\ln(q)\sin(\pi|x|)} q^{\frac{x^2-|x|}{2}} H(x, q)$$

for $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}$, $q \in (0, 1)$, where

$$H(x, q) = \exp\left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 - \cos(2\pi kx)}{k} \left(\coth\left(\frac{2\pi^2 k}{\ln q}\right) + 1\right)\right).$$

Further examples show that the correction factor $H_f(x)$ may be explicit, quantitatively small, or identically equal to 1. In the latter case, the framework yields the new law:

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sum_{k=1}^{-j/n} \arctan\left(\frac{2k^2}{m^2}\right) \equiv 0, \quad n, m \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}.$$

In the tanh case, we find

$$\prod_{k=1}^x \tanh(k/2) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} \tanh(k/2) = \frac{2\pi \tanh(x/2)}{\sin(\pi x)} (1 + O(10^{-8}))$$

which strongly resembles the classical Euler's reflection.

Finally, we pose an open problem of whether there exists a non trivial Eulerian function for which $H_h(x) \equiv 1$.

1.3 Structure of the article

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 recalls the Müller-Schleicher's definitions and properties used throughout the paper. Section 3 records the continuous-product representation of the sine function. Section 4 proves the general reflection principle and the Fourier representation of H_f . Section 5 treats the Eulerian case. Section 6 recovers Euler's reflection formula in squared form. Section 7 proves the multiplication theorem. Section 8 proves the q-Gamma identity. Section 9 treats the main applications. Section 10 discusses how Müller and Schleicher's theory provides a unified language to describe many special functions.

2 Müller-Schleicher calculus

We recall the part of Müller-Schleicher theory which is needed below [7]. Throughout the paper, \sum indicates the continuous sum, \prod the corresponding continuous

product, and $\overline{\sum}$ the continuous sum of a polynomial. Thus, when p is a polynomial,

$$\overline{\sum}_{k=a}^b p(k)$$

denotes the polynomial continuation of the ordinary finite sum.

Polynomial sums. Before recalling Müller and Schleicher's definition, we fix the notation for polynomial sums. If P is any polynomial that satisfies

$$P(t) - P(t - 1) = p(t),$$

then we set

$$\overline{\sum}_{k=a}^b p(k) := P(b) - P(a - 1).$$

This agrees with the ordinary finite sum whenever a, b are integers with $a \leq b$.

Thus, for instance,

$$\overline{\sum}_{k=a}^b 1 = b - a + 1.$$

2.1 Continuous sums

Let $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be such that

$$x \in U \implies x + 1 \in U.$$

Definition 2.1 (Sum admissibility). Let $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. We say that f is admissible of degree at most d if there exists a sequence of polynomials $(p_N)_{N \geq 1}$, each of degree at most d , such that

$$f(N + x) - p_N(N + x) \longrightarrow 0 \quad (N \rightarrow +\infty)$$

for every fixed $x \in U$.

Definition 2.2 (Continuous sum). Let $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be admissible. We say that f is summable if, for every $a, b + 1 \in U$, the limit

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \left(\overline{\sum}_{k=N+a}^{N+b} p_N(k) + \sum_{k=1}^N (f(k + a - 1) - f(k + b)) \right)$$

exists. In that case, we define (see [7, p.126, Definition 3])

$$\overline{\sum}_{k=a}^b f(k) := \lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \left(\overline{\sum}_{k=N+a}^{N+b} p_N(k) + \sum_{k=1}^N (f(k + a - 1) - f(k + b)) \right).$$

Müller and Schleicher prove that the value of the sum is independent of the chosen approximating polynomials. Moreover, if $b - a \in \mathbb{N}$, the definition agrees with the ordinary finite sum; if f itself is a polynomial, then $\overline{\sum} f = \sum f$.

2.2 Continuous products

The multiplicative theory is obtained by exponentiating continuous sums of logarithms.

Definition 2.3 (Product-admissible functions). Let $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$. We say that f is product-admissible if there exists a summable function $L : U \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ such that

$$e^{L(x)} = f(x), \quad x \in U.$$

Thus, we define (see [7, p.126, Definition 3])

$$\prod_{k=a}^b f(k) := \exp \left(\sum_{k=a}^b L(k) \right).$$

All identities involving continuous products are intended with respect to the chosen logarithm. In the real positive case, we always take $L = \ln f$.

Equivalently, if p_N is an approximating polynomial sequence for L , then

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) = \lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \exp \left(\sum_{k=N+1}^{N+x} p_N(k) \right) \prod_{k=1}^N \frac{f(k)}{f(k+x)}.$$

2.3 Basic rules

Now, we present the elementary rules used throughout the paper.

Proposition 2.4 (Product rules). *Let $f, g : U \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$ be product-admissible. Then, whenever the quantities involved are defined, the following properties hold.*

1. If $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then

$$\prod_{k=1}^n f(k) = \prod_{k=1}^n f(k).$$

2. For all $x, y \in U$

$$\prod_{k=1}^{x+y} f(k) = \prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^y f(k+x).$$

3. If the logarithm of fg is chosen as $L_f + L_g$, then

$$\prod_{k=a}^b f(k) \prod_{k=a}^b g(k) = \prod_{k=a}^b f(k)g(k).$$

4. Shifts, inverses and quotients of product-admissible functions are product-admissible on their common zero-free domains.

Proof. These identities follow immediately from the corresponding continuation, translation and linearity properties of Müller and Schleicher continuous sums, applied to the chosen logarithms (see [7, p.129, Theorem 5]). \square

2.4 Residual representation

Definition 2.5 (Residual product). Let f be product-admissible, with respect to a chosen summable logarithm L . Whenever the limit exists, define the residual function

$$\pi_f(x) := \lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \prod_{k=1}^x f(k+N).$$

Proposition 2.6 (Residual representation). *Assume that all quantities involved are defined, and that f is product admissible. Let L be the chosen summable logarithm of f , and let (p_N) be an approximating polynomial sequence for L . Then*

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) = \pi_f(x) \lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \prod_{k=1}^N \frac{f(k)}{f(k+x)}.$$

In terms of the Müller-Schleicher definition, the residual factor corresponds to the asymptotic polynomial contribution

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \exp \left(\sum_{k=N+1}^{N+x} p_N(k) \right),$$

where (p_N) approximates the chosen logarithm L .

Proof. Set

$$P_f(x) := \prod_{k=1}^x f(k).$$

By the continuation rule,

$$P_f(N+x) = P_f(N) \prod_{k=1}^x f(k+N),$$

and also

$$P_f(N+x) = P_f(x) \prod_{k=1}^N f(k+x).$$

Solving for $P_f(x)$, we obtain

$$P_f(x) = \left(\prod_{k=1}^x f(k+N) \right) \prod_{k=1}^N \frac{f(k)}{f(k+x)}.$$

Passing to the limit gives the desired formula. \square

The residual is particularly simple when the logarithm is asymptotically a constant.

Lemma 2.7 (Approximately constant residual). *Let f be product-admissible with chosen logarithm L . Suppose that there exists $C \in \mathbb{C}$ such that*

$$L(N + x) \longrightarrow C \quad (N \rightarrow +\infty)$$

for every fixed x . Then

$$\pi_f(x) = e^{Cx}.$$

Proof. The logarithm $L(N + x)$ converges pointwise to the constant function C . Since the continuous sum of the constant function C over an interval of length x is Cx , the residual product is e^{Cx} . \square

2.5 Examples

The basic example is

$$\prod_{k=1}^x k = \Gamma(x + 1), \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{-1, -2, \dots\}.$$

Thus, the Müller-Schleicher product extends the factorial product (see [7, p.128, Example 4]).

As a second illustration, let $f(t) = \arctan t$ on $(0, \infty)$. Since

$$\arctan(N + a) \longrightarrow \frac{\pi}{2},$$

the residual lemma gives

$$\prod_{k=1}^x \arctan(k) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^x \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\arctan(k)}{\arctan(k + x)}, \quad x > -1.$$

For $x \in \mathbb{N}$, the infinite product telescopes and one recovers the ordinary finite product.

3 Sine function as a continuous product

Euler's reflection formula

$$\Gamma(1 - z)\Gamma(z) = \frac{\pi}{\sin(\pi z)} \tag{1}$$

is one of the most celebrated identities in analysis, connecting factorial-like structures with trigonometric functions. In this section, we investigate whether similar reflection properties can be extended to more general classes of products and summations.

We shall use the following lemmas.

Lemma 3.1 (Reflection of a continuous product). *When $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$ is product-admissible, then for all $x \in U$*

$$\prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \prod_{k=1}^x \frac{1}{f(k-x)}$$

and thus

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \prod_{k=1}^x \frac{f(k)}{f(k-x)}.$$

Proof. Since for $x, y \in U$

$$\prod_{k=1}^{x+y} f(k) = \prod_{k=1}^y f(k) \prod_{k=1}^x f(k+y),$$

when f is product admissible, we choose $y = -x$, then

$$\prod_{k=1}^0 f(k) = 1 = \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) \prod_{k=1}^x f(k-x),$$

and

$$\prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \prod_{k=1}^x \frac{1}{f(k-x)}.$$

This proves the claim. □

Lemma 3.2 (Sine function as a continuous product).

$$\sin x = x \prod_{k=1}^{x/\pi} \left(1 - \frac{x}{\pi k}\right), \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \pi\mathbb{Z}.$$

Proof. We recall

$$\Gamma(1-x)\Gamma(1+x) = \frac{\pi x}{\sin(\pi x)}.$$

Since for any real x in the domain of Gamma it holds

$$\Gamma(x+1) = \prod_{k=1}^x k,$$

then by the previous lemma

$$\Gamma(1-x) = \prod_{k=1}^{-x} k = \prod_{k=1}^x \frac{1}{k-x},$$

and

$$\Gamma(1-x)\Gamma(1+x) = \prod_{k=1}^x \frac{k}{k-x} = \frac{\pi x}{\sin(\pi x)}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\pi x \prod_{k=1}^x \frac{k-x}{k} = \pi x \prod_{k=1}^x \left(1 - \frac{x}{k}\right) = \sin(\pi x).$$

If we replace x by x/π , we immediately obtain the continuous product representation

$$\sin x = x \prod_{k=1}^{x/\pi} \left(1 - \frac{x}{\pi k}\right), \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \pi\mathbb{Z}.$$

□

Corollary 3.3. *In particular, we obtain*

$$\prod_{k=1}^{1/2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2k}\right) = \frac{2}{\pi}, \quad \prod_{k=1}^{1/3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{3k}\right) = \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi},$$

and

$$\prod_{k=1}^{1/2} \frac{8k}{2k-1} = \pi.$$

4 General representation for non-Eulerian reflections

4.1 Assumptions on f and reflected residual

Definition 4.1. We call $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ *reflective* if it has the following properties:

1. f is product-admissible;
2. f is even and positive;
3. $f(x)$ is *slowly varying*, in the sense that for any $x \in \mathbb{R}$ one has $\frac{f(N+x)}{f(N)} \rightarrow 1$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$;
4. $\ln f \in C^2(\mathbb{R})$, and $(\ln f)''(x) \in L^1(0, \infty)$.

Proposition 4.2. *Let $\pi_{f\pm}(x)$ be the residual of $\prod_{k=1}^x \frac{f(k)}{f(k-x)}$. If $f(x)$ is reflective, then $\pi_{f\pm}(x) = 1$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$, and therefore*

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{f^2(k)}{f(k+x)f(k-x)} \quad x \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Proof. Since a reflective function is also product admissible, its reflected product will be

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \prod_{k=1}^x \frac{f(k)}{f(k-x)}.$$

Using Müller's method and our residual representation, it can be rewritten by the limit

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^x \frac{f(k+N)}{f(k-x+N)} \right) \left(\prod_{k=1}^N \frac{f^2(k)}{f(k+x)f(k-x)} \right),$$

where the first factor is the residual term; its logarithmic convergence is going to be proved in Lemma 4.7.

Now, set $g_x(k) = \ln \frac{f(k)}{f(k-x)}$ for each fixed $x \in \mathbb{R}$ for a chosen logarithm; thus, for all $r \in \mathbb{R}$, one has

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} g_x(N+r) = \ln \frac{f(N+r)}{f(N+r-x)} = \ln 1 = 0$$

by slow variation. Hence, we are in the approximately constant case for which Lemma 2.7 ensures that the residual will be $\pi_{f^\pm}(x) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{f(N)}{f(N-x)} \right)^x \equiv 1$. This proves the claim. \square

4.2 Telescoping

Definition 4.3. For a reflective function, we define

$$\Pi_f(x) = \prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k)$$

Lemma 4.4. Let $f(x)$ be a reflective function $\mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$. Then for every natural number n we have

$$\Pi_f(n) = \frac{f(n)}{f(0)}.$$

Proof. As shown above, under the present assumptions, we have $\pi_{f^\pm}(x) \equiv 1$, while for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_f(n) &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{k=1}^N \frac{f^2(k)}{f(k+n)f(k-n)} \\ &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f^2(1)f^2(2) \cdots f^2(n-1)f^2(n)f^2(n+1) \cdots f^2(N)}{f(1+n)f(1-n)f(2+n)f(2-n) \cdots f(N+n)f(N-n)}. \end{aligned}$$

Since f is even and positive, almost all factors in the denominator cancel with those in the numerator, leaving only a few residual terms:

$$\Pi_f(n) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(n)}{f(0)} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f(N-k)}{f(N+k+1)}.$$

The product $\prod_{k=0}^{n-1} f(N-k)/f(N+k+1)$ has a finite index, so it tends to 1 as $N \rightarrow \infty$ due to the slow variation of f , and the claim follows. \square

4.3 The 1-periodicity of the ratio

Proposition 4.5. *Let*

$$Q(x) = \frac{\Pi_f(x)}{f(x)} = \prod_{k=1}^{x-1} f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k).$$

If $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ is reflective, then $Q(x)$ is 1-periodic. In particular, for every natural number n and for every $x \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$Q(x+n) = Q(x).$$

Proof. Consider the ratio

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Pi_f(x+1)}{\Pi_f(x)} &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^N \frac{f^2(k)}{f(k+x+1)f(k-x-1)} \cdot \frac{f(k+x)f(k-x)}{f^2(k)} \right) \\ &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{k=1}^N \frac{f(k+x)f(k-x)}{f(k+x+1)f(k-x-1)}, \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}. \end{aligned}$$

Expanding the product, we obtain the following.

$$\frac{\Pi_f(x+1)}{\Pi_f(x)} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(1+x)f(N-x)}{f(-x)f(N+1+x)} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(1+x)f(N-x)}{f(x)f(N+1+x)}.$$

Since f is slowly varying, the ratio $f(N-x)/f(N+1+x)$ tends to 1 as $N \rightarrow \infty$, hence

$$\frac{\Pi_f(x+1)}{\Pi_f(x)} = \frac{f(x+1)}{f(x)}, \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Now consider

$$\frac{\Pi_f(x+2)}{\Pi_f(x)} = \frac{\Pi_f(x+2)}{\Pi_f(x+1)} \cdot \frac{\Pi_f(x+1)}{\Pi_f(x)} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(x+2)}{f(x)} \prod_{k=0}^1 \frac{f(N-x-k)}{f(N+x+k+1)}.$$

In general, by induction on n one obtains

$$\frac{\Pi_f(x+n)}{\Pi_f(x)} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(x+n)}{f(x)} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f(N-x-k)}{f(N+x+k+1)}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Dividing by $f(x+n)$ we get

$$\frac{\Pi_f(x+n)}{f(x+n)} = \frac{\Pi_f(x)}{f(x)} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{f(N-x-k)}{f(N+x+k+1)} \rightarrow \frac{\Pi_f(x)}{f(x)}, \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

which shows that $Q(x+n) = Q(x)$ for every integer n . Hence Q is 1-periodic. \square

4.4 The Fourier expansion

Lemma 4.6. *Let $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ be a reflective function and let $g(x) = \ln f(x)$. Let*

$$M = \int_0^\infty |g''(x)| dx,$$

and

$$A_k^f := \frac{2}{\pi k} \int_0^\infty g'(t) \sin(2\pi kt) dt.$$

Therefore,

$$|A_k^f| \leq \frac{M}{\pi^2 k^2},$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^\infty |A_k^f| \leq \frac{M}{6}.$$

Proof. Since $g'' \in L^1(0, \infty)$, the function g' has a finite limit at $+\infty$. On the other hand, the slow variation of f implies

$$g(N+x) - g(N) \rightarrow 0 \quad (N \rightarrow \infty)$$

for every fixed x , hence necessarily

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} g'(t) = 0.$$

Moreover, since f is even and positive, g is even, so

$$g'(0) = 0.$$

Integrating by parts A_k^f gives

$$A_k^f = \frac{-g'(t) \cos(2\pi kt)}{\pi^2 k^2} \Big|_0^\infty + \frac{1}{\pi^2 k^2} \int_0^\infty g''(t) \cos(2\pi kt) dt.$$

The first part is simply $\frac{g'(0)}{\pi^2 k^2} = 0$ as f is even. The second term is instead

$$\frac{1}{\pi^2 k^2} \int_0^\infty g''(t) \cos(2\pi kt) dt \leq \frac{1}{\pi^2 k^2} \int_0^\infty |g''(t)| dt = \frac{M}{\pi^2 k^2} < \infty.$$

Hence, A_k^f is finite and has the bound $|A_k^f| \leq \frac{M}{\pi^2 k^2}$. Finally,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |A_k^f| \leq \frac{M}{\pi^2} \cdot \frac{\pi^2}{6} = \frac{M}{6}.$$

□

Lemma 4.7 (Uniform convergence of the reflected logarithmic series). *Let f be a reflective function and let $g(x) = \ln f(x)$. Then, for $x \in [0, 1]$, the series*

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (2g(m) - g(m-x) - g(m+x))$$

converges uniformly. Therefore, it may be differentiated term by term once, and

$$\frac{d}{dx} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (2g(m) - g(m-x) - g(m+x)) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (g'(m-x) - g'(m+x)),$$

where the differentiated series also converges uniformly on $[0, 1]$.

Proof. For $x \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$2g(m) - g(m-x) - g(m+x) = - \int_0^x \int_{m-s}^{m+s} g''(t) dt ds.$$

Hence

$$|2g(m) - g(m-x) - g(m+x)| \leq \int_{m-1}^{m+1} |g''(t)| dt = M_m$$

Since

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \int_{m-1}^{m+1} |g''(t)| dt = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} M_m \leq 2 \int_0^{\infty} |g''(t)| dt < \infty,$$

the original series converges uniformly by the Weierstrass M-test ([8, Theorem 7.10]).

Similarly,

$$|g'(m-x) - g'(m+x)| \leq \int_{m-x}^{m+x} |g''(t)| dt \leq \int_{m-1}^{m+1} |g''(t)| dt.$$

Therefore, the differentiated series also converges uniformly on $[0, 1]$. The termwise differentiation follows from the standard theorem on uniformly convergent series of derivatives. □

4.5 Fourier representation of the correction factor

We now derive the Fourier representation of the correction factor.

Throughout this subsection, we write

$$g(x) := \ln f(x).$$

Since f is positive and even, g has a real range, and it is even. Recall that

$$\Pi_f(x) = \prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k),$$

and define the correction factor by

$$H_f(x) := \frac{f(0)}{f(x)} \Pi_f(x).$$

Theorem 4.8 (Fourier representation of the correction factor). *Let $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ be reflective, and set $g = \ln f$. Then, for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$,*

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \frac{f(x)}{f(0)} H_f(x)$$

where

$$H_f(x) = \exp \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k^f (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1) \right),$$

and

$$A_k^f = \frac{2}{\pi k} \int_0^{\infty} g'(t) \sin(2\pi kt) dt.$$

Proof. Set $\ln H_f(x) = \Phi(x)$. By the reflection formula, we have

$$\Phi_f(x) = g(0) - g(x) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (2g(m) - g(m-x) - g(m+x)). \quad (4.9)$$

By the previous lemma, this series converges uniformly on $[0, 1]$, and it may be differentiated term by term. Therefore

$$\Phi_f'(x) = -g'(x) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (g'(m-x) - g'(m+x)). \quad (4.10)$$

We now compute the real Fourier coefficients of Φ_f . For $k \geq 1$, define

$$a_k(\Phi_f) := 2 \int_0^1 \Phi_f(x) \cos(2\pi kx) dx,$$

and

$$b_k(\Phi_f) := 2 \int_0^1 \Phi_f(x) \sin(2\pi kx) dx.$$

First, integrating by parts gives

$$a_k(\Phi_f) = -\frac{1}{\pi k} \int_0^1 \Phi'_f(x) \sin(2\pi kx) dx. \quad (4.11)$$

Using (4.10), and integrating the uniformly convergent series term by term, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \Phi'_f(x) \sin(2\pi kx) dx &= -\int_0^1 g'(x) \sin(2\pi kx) dx \\ &+ \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \int_0^1 (g'(m-x) - g'(m+x)) \sin(2\pi kx) dx, \end{aligned}$$

For the first integral, set $t = m - x$. Since

$$\sin(2\pi k(m-t)) = -\sin(2\pi kt),$$

we get

$$\int_0^1 g'(m-x) \sin(2\pi kx) dx = -\int_{m-1}^m g'(t) \sin(2\pi kt) dt.$$

For the second term, set $t = m + x$. Since

$$\sin(2\pi k(t-m)) = \sin(2\pi kt),$$

we get

$$-\int_0^1 g'(m+x) \sin(2\pi kx) dx = -\int_m^{m+1} g'(t) \sin(2\pi kt) dt.$$

Hence, after summing and passing to the limit,

$$\int_0^1 \Phi'_f(x) \sin(2\pi kx) dx = -2 \int_0^{\infty} g'(t) \sin(2\pi kt) dt.$$

Therefore

$$a_k(\Phi_f) = \frac{2}{\pi k} \int_0^{\infty} g'(t) \sin(2\pi kt) dt = A_k^f. \quad (4.12)$$

Now we compute the sine coefficients. Since H_f is 1-periodic and $H_f(0) = 1$, we have $\Phi_f(1) = \Phi_f(0) = 0$. Hence, the boundary term in the integration by parts vanishes, and

$$b_k(\Phi_f) = \frac{1}{\pi k} \int_0^1 \Phi'_f(x) \cos(2\pi kx) dx.$$

Using (4.10) and the same changes of variables, we obtain

$$\int_0^1 \Phi'_f(x) \cos(2\pi kx) dx = 0.$$

Indeed, for the partial sums up to N , the integral reduces to

$$- \int_N^{N+1} g'(t) \cos(2\pi kt) dt,$$

which tends to 0, since $g'(t) \rightarrow 0$. Therefore

$$b_k(\Phi_f) = 0.$$

Now define

$$S(x) := \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k^f (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1).$$

By Lemma 4.6,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |A_k^f| < \infty,$$

so S is continuous and 1-periodic. Moreover, termwise integration is allowed, and therefore

$$a_k(S) = A_k^f, \quad b_k(S) = 0 \quad (k \geq 1).$$

Thus Φ_f and S have the same non-constant real Fourier coefficients. By the uniqueness theorem for Fourier coefficients of continuous periodic functions ([9, Ch.2]), $\Phi_f - S$ is constant.

Finally,

$$\Phi_f(0) = \ln H_f(0) = 0,$$

and

$$S(0) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k^f (1 - 1) = 0.$$

Therefore the constant is zero, and so

$$\Phi_f(x) = S(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k^f (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1).$$

The identity has been proved on $[0, 1]$. Since both sides are continuous and 1-periodic, it extends to all $x \in \mathbb{R}$. \square

Remark 4.9. From Lemma 4.6, using $g = \ln f$ we immediately have the bound

$$e^{-\|g''\|_1/3} \leq H_f(x) \leq e^{\|g''\|_1/3}.$$

Indeed,

$$|\ln H_f(x)| = \left| \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k^f (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1) \right| \leq 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |A_k^f| \leq \frac{\|g''\|_1}{3}$$

5 Generalizing Euler's reflection scheme

In the case where $f(0) = 0$, the situation becomes more interesting. f may vanish at the origin, hence it is not product-admissible on all of \mathbb{R} . We only require product admissibility on zero-free shift domains. More precisely, for f itself we use

$$U = \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0, -1, -2, \dots\}.$$

Definition 5.1. We call $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ an *Eulerian reflective* function if and only if it has the following properties:

1. $f(x) = 0 \iff x = 0$.
2. $f(x)$ is product admissible in U specified above.
3. There exist a natural $r \geq 1$ and a real $\lambda > 0$ such that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{f(x)}{x^r} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^-} \frac{f(x)}{x^r} = \lambda.$$

- 4.

$$h(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{f(x)}{x^r} & x \neq 0 \\ \lambda & x = 0 \end{cases}$$

is a reflective function.

In this definition, the sign and symmetry assumptions are imposed on h , rather than on f .

Theorem 5.2 (Eulerian reflection). *Let $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an Eulerian reflective function. Define*

$$h(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{f(x)}{x^r} & x \neq 0 \\ \lambda & x = 0 \end{cases}$$

for $r : \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x)}{x^r} = \lambda > 0$. Then, for all $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}$,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \frac{\pi^r f(x)}{\lambda \sin^r(\pi x)} H_h(x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z} \quad (2)$$

where H_h is the 1-periodic correction factor associated with h , given by Theorem 4.8.

Proof. From the previous sections, we know that when $f(x)$ is reflective,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \frac{f(x)}{f(0)} H_f(x), \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R},$$

where H_f is the 1-periodic factor.

In the present situation $f(0) = 0$, so we introduce the auxiliary function

$$h(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{f(x)}{x^r} & x \neq 0 \\ \lambda & x = 0 \end{cases}$$

which is reflective by hypothesis.

Therefore,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x h(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} h(k) = \frac{h(x)}{h(0)} H_h(x) = \frac{f(x)}{\lambda x^r} H_h(x).$$

On the other hand,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x h(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} h(k) = \prod_{k=1}^x \frac{f(k)}{k^r} \prod_{k=1}^{-x} \frac{f(k)}{k^r} = \prod_{k=1}^x \frac{f(k)(k-x)^r}{f(k-x)k^r}.$$

Hence,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x \frac{f(k)(k-x)^r}{f(k-x)k^r} = \frac{f(x)}{\lambda x^r} H_h(x).$$

Now, $t(k) = \frac{k}{k-x}$ is product admissible for $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}$, and f is also product admissible in U . Since $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z} \implies x \in U$, we can separate the terms under the same restricted domain, and hence

$$\prod_{k=1}^x \frac{f(k)}{f(k-x)} = \frac{f(x)}{\lambda x^r} H_h(x) \left(\prod_{k=1}^x \frac{k}{k-x} \right)^r.$$

By the classical Euler product in Lemma 3.2,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x \frac{k}{k-x} = \frac{\pi x}{\sin(\pi x)}$$

and thus

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \frac{\pi^r f(x)}{\lambda \sin^r(\pi x)} H_h(x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}. \quad (3)$$

This completes the proof. \square

Remark 5.3. Note that, when $r = 0$, f belongs to the reflective class. In this case, the formula above provides $h(x) \equiv f(x)$ and $\lambda = f(0)$, so the principal part becomes $f(x)/f(0)$. Indeed, although this formula is a consequence of our reflection theorem, it also contains it.

5.1 Non-even functions

Definition 5.4 (Non-even Eulerian functions). We call f a non-even Eulerian function if f satisfies the Eulerian conditions of Definition 5.1, except that the auxiliary function

$$h(x) = \begin{cases} f(x)/x^r, & x \neq 0, \\ \lambda, & x = 0, \end{cases}$$

is not required to be even. Instead, we assume that, on $[0, \infty)$, h is positive, slowly varying, and if $g = \ln h$, then

$$g \in C([0, \infty)) \cap C^2((0, \infty)), \quad g'(0^+) \text{ exists}, \quad g'(t) \rightarrow 0, \quad g'' \in L^1(0, \infty).$$

In this case, the Fourier argument of Theorem 4.8 applies on the fundamental interval $0 < x \leq 1$. The only difference is the boundary term that comes from $g'(0^+)$.

Proposition 5.5. *Let $f(x)$ be a non-even Eulerian function such that $h(0) = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} f(x)/x^r = \lambda > 0$ for some natural $r \geq 0$. Let $g(x) = \ln h(x)$, $\alpha = g'(0^+)$ and*

$$B_k = \frac{1}{k^2 \pi^2} \int_0^\infty g''(t) \cos(2\pi kt) dt$$

Then it holds

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \frac{\pi^r f(|x|)}{\lambda \sin^r(\pi|x|)} e^{\alpha(x^2-|x|)} H_h^B(x), \quad x \in (-1, 1) \setminus \{0\},$$

where

$$H_h^B(x) = \exp\left(\sum_{k=1}^\infty B_k (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1)\right),$$

which again satisfies the bound $|\ln H_h^B(x)| \leq \frac{\|g''\|_1}{3}$.

This is the form used to treat the q-Gamma case.

Proof. It is enough to prove the formula for $0 < x < 1$, because the case $-1 < x < 0$ follows from the symmetry

$$\Pi_f(-x) = \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) \prod_{k=1}^x f(k) = \Pi_f(x).$$

Set

$$h(t) = \frac{f(t)}{t^r}, \quad g(t) = \ln h(t), \quad t > 0.$$

For $0 \leq x \leq 1$, all the arguments $m-x$ and $m+x$ appearing in the reflected logarithmic series belong to $[0, \infty)$. Hence, the uniform convergence and termwise differentiation argument used in Lemma 4.7 applies unchanged in this setting.

Thus, the logarithm of the correction factor associated with h has the Fourier representation

$$\Phi_h(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1),$$

where

$$A_k = \frac{2}{\pi k} \int_0^{\infty} g'(t) \sin(2\pi kt) dt.$$

The only difference from the even case is the integration by parts of A_k . Indeed, integrating on $[0^+, \infty]$ gives

$$A_k = \frac{\alpha}{\pi^2 k^2} + \frac{1}{\pi^2 k^2} \int_0^{\infty} g''(t) \cos(2\pi kt) dt = \frac{\alpha}{\pi^2 k^2} + B_k,$$

where

$$\alpha = g'(0^+), \quad B_k = \frac{1}{\pi^2 k^2} \int_0^{\infty} g''(t) \cos(2\pi kt) dt.$$

Therefore

$$\Phi_h(x) = \frac{\alpha}{\pi^2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi kx) - 1}{k^2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} B_k (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1).$$

Using the classical Fourier identity

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi kx) - 1}{k^2} = \pi^2 (x^2 - x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1,$$

we find

$$\Phi_h(x) = \alpha(x^2 - x) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} B_k (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1).$$

Hence, for $0 < x < 1$,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x h(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} h(k) = \frac{h(x)}{\lambda} e^{\alpha(x^2 - x)} H_h^B(x),$$

where

$$H_h^B(x) = \exp \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} B_k (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1) \right).$$

Since $f(t) = t^r h(t)$, we separate the Eulerian part as in the proof above, obtaining

$$\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} f(k) = \frac{\pi^r f(x)}{\lambda \sin^r(\pi x)} e^{\alpha(x^2 - x)} H_h^B(x), \quad 0 < x < 1.$$

Now, since the term on the left is even, while the right term is not, replacing x by $|x|$ gives the stated formula on $(-1, 1) \setminus \{0\}$. \square

6 Recovering Euler

6.0.1 The continuous product of $k^2 + a$

Proposition 6.1. *Let $a \in (0, \infty)$. Then for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$*

$$\prod_{k=1}^x (k^2 + a) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} (k^2 + a) = \frac{(x^2/a + 1)(1 - e^{-2\pi\sqrt{a}})^2}{1 - 2e^{-2\pi\sqrt{a}} \cos(2\pi x) + e^{-4\pi\sqrt{a}}} \quad (4)$$

Proof. Let

$$f(k) = k^2 + a,$$

where $a > 0$. In this situation, f is product admissible, since its logarithm is summable. Moreover, the function is positive, $\ln f \in C^2$ and $(\ln f)'' \in L^1$. Slow variation is given by

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a + (x + N)^2}{a + N^2} = 1,$$

for every finite $x, a \in \mathbb{R}$. Therefore, the function is reflective, and its product takes the form

$$\prod_{k=1}^x (k^2 + a) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} (k^2 + a) = \frac{x^2 + a}{a} e^{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1)}, \quad \forall a > 0, x \in \mathbb{R},$$

with

$$A_k = \frac{2}{\pi k} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{2t}{t^2 + a} \sin(2\pi kt) dt.$$

The value of the integral above is known (see [5, 3.723 (3), p.424])

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{t}{t^2 + a} \sin(2\pi kt) dt = \frac{\pi}{2} e^{-2\pi k\sqrt{a}}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}, a \in \mathbb{R}^+.$$

Now, multiplying by $4/(\pi k)$ gives

$$A_k = \frac{2e^{-2\pi k\sqrt{a}}}{k}.$$

The sum becomes

$$S_a(x) = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-2\pi k\sqrt{a}}}{k} (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1).$$

Separate into two sums:

$$S_a(x) = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-2\pi k\sqrt{a}}}{k} \cos(2\pi kx) - 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-2\pi k\sqrt{a}}}{k}.$$

The second sum is

$$S_2(r) = -2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{r^k}{k} = 2 \ln(1 - r), \quad r = e^{-2\pi\sqrt{a}},$$

since r lies inside the radius of convergence.

The first term is

$$S_1(r, \lambda) = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{r^k}{k} \cos(\lambda k), \quad \lambda = 2\pi x.$$

This converges for $a > 0$, so we set $a \in (0, \infty)$.

Using complex numbers,

$$\begin{aligned} \cos(\lambda k) &= \Re(e^{i\lambda k}), & S_1(r, \lambda) &= 2\Re\left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(re^{i\lambda})^k}{k}\right) = 2\Re(-\ln(1 - re^{i\lambda})) \\ & & &= -\ln(1 - 2r \cos(\lambda) + r^2) = -\ln(1 - 2r \cos(2\pi x) + r^2), \end{aligned}$$

and finally,

$$S_a(x) = \ln(1 - r)^2 - \ln(1 - 2r \cos(2\pi x) + r^2).$$

The result follows. □

This identity, recoverable classically via the Gamma function [4, §5.5(i), Eq. (5.5.1); §5.5(ii), Eq. (5.5.3)], here emerges as a direct output of the reflection theorem, illustrating the systematic nature of the framework.

6.0.2 The square of Euler's reflection formula

Using the previous formula, it is natural to see how the square of Euler's reflection formula happens to be a special case of our analytic framework. In fact, taking the limit as $a \rightarrow 0^+$ gives

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow 0^+} \prod_{k=1}^x (k^2 + a) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} (k^2 + a) = \prod_{k=1}^x k^2 \prod_{k=1}^{-x} k^2 = \lim_{a \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{(x^2 + a)(1 - e^{-2\pi\sqrt{a}})^2}{a(1 - 2e^{-2\pi\sqrt{a}} \cos(2\pi x) + e^{-4\pi\sqrt{a}})}$$

That is,

$$\left(\prod_{k=1}^x k \prod_{k=1}^{-x} k \right)^2 = \lim_{a \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{x^2 (-2\pi\sqrt{a})^2}{2a(1 - \cos(2\pi x))} = \frac{2x^2\pi^2}{1 - \cos(2\pi x)} = \frac{x^2\pi^2}{\sin^2(\pi x)}$$

for $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}$.

Note that in this proof, we have only used our reflection theorem. Thus, we have just shown how it recovers Euler's result independently, without any circularity.

7 A Gauss-type Multiplication Theorem

7.1 Preparatory Lemmas

Lemma 7.1 (Sums of cosines). *Let*

$$H(x) = \exp \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1) \right).$$

Then, if n is odd,

$$\prod_{j=1}^{(n-1)/2} H(j/n) = \exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1 : n \nmid k} A_k \right).$$

If n is even,

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n/2-1} H(j/n) = \exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1 : n \nmid k} A_k + \sum_{k \geq 1 : k \text{ odd}} A_k \right).$$

Proof. We have

$$\ln \prod_j H(j/n) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k \sum_j \left(\cos \frac{2\pi k j}{n} - 1 \right).$$

Assume first that n is odd. The standard cosine sum gives

$$\sum_{j=1}^{(n-1)/2} \cos \frac{2\pi k j}{n} = \begin{cases} \frac{n-1}{2}, & n \mid k, \\ -\frac{1}{2}, & n \nmid k. \end{cases}$$

Hence

$$\sum_{j=1}^{(n-1)/2} \left(\cos \frac{2\pi k j}{n} - 1 \right) = \begin{cases} 0, & n \mid k, \\ -\frac{n}{2}, & n \nmid k. \end{cases}$$

Therefore

$$\prod_{j=1}^{(n-1)/2} H(j/n) = \exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1 : n \nmid k} A_k \right).$$

Now assume that n is even. The standard cosine sum gives

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n/2-1} \cos \frac{2\pi k j}{n} = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} - 1, & n \mid k, \\ -1, & n \nmid k, k \text{ even}, \\ 0, & k \text{ odd}. \end{cases}$$

Hence

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n/2-1} \left(\cos \frac{2\pi kj}{n} - 1 \right) = \begin{cases} 0, & n \mid k, \\ -\frac{n}{2}, & n \nmid k, k \text{ even}, \\ 1 - \frac{n}{2}, & k \text{ odd}. \end{cases}$$

Thus

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k \sum_{j=1}^{n/2-1} \left(\cos \frac{2\pi kj}{n} - 1 \right) = -\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1: n \nmid k} A_k + \sum_{k \geq 1: k \text{ odd}} A_k.$$

This proves the even case. \square

7.2 Gauss-type multiplication formulas

Theorem 7.2 (Multiplication formula for reflective functions). *Let $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ be a reflective function. Thus, for $n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2$,*

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} f(k) = f(0)^{\frac{1-n}{2}} \exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1: n \nmid k} A_k^f \right).$$

Proof for odd n Define $\prod_{k=1}^x f(k) = P_f(x)$. If $n-1$ is even, then

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{j=1}^{n-1} P_f(-j/n) &= P_f(-1/n) P_f(-2/n) \dots P_f((2-n)/n) P_f((1-n)/n) \\ &= P_f(-1/n) P_f(-2/n) \dots P_f(2/n-1) P_f(1/n-1). \end{aligned}$$

Note that we can pair them in $(n-1)/2$ reflection terms. Indeed, by the one-step product rule,

$$P_f(a) = P_f(a-1) f(a),$$

hence

$$P_f(a-1) = \frac{P_f(a)}{f(a)}.$$

Since f is even, $f(a) = f(-a)$. Hence,

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} P_f(-j/n) = \prod_{j=1}^{(n-1)/2} P_f(-j/n) P_f(j/n) \prod_{j=1}^{(n-1)/2} \frac{1}{f(-j/n)}$$

Now, since f is reflective, $P_f(-j/n) P_f(j/n) = \frac{f(j/n)}{f(0)} H_f(j/n)$ and thus

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} P_f(-j/n) = f(0)^{\frac{1-n}{2}} \prod_{j=1}^{(n-1)/2} \frac{f(j/n) H_f(j/n)}{f(-j/n)}$$

Since f is even, we only have for odd $n > 1 \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} P_f(-j/n) = f(0)^{\frac{1-n}{2}} \prod_{j=1}^{(n-1)/2} H_f(j/n).$$

By the previous lemma, one gets the following.

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} f(k) = f(0)^{\frac{1-n}{2}} \exp\left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1: n \nmid k} A_k^f\right)$$

for odd, natural $n > 1$.

Proof for even n If $n - 1$ is odd, then we can pair them in $n/2 - 1$ reflection terms, except for the central one. Indeed,

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} P_f(-j/n) = P_f(-1/n) \dots P_f(-1/2) \dots P_f(1/n - 1)$$

that is,

$$\begin{aligned} &= P_f(-1/2) \prod_{j=1}^{n/2-1} P_f(-j/n) P_f(j/n) \prod_{j=1}^{n/2-1} \frac{1}{f(-j/n)} \\ &= f(0)^{1-n/2} P_f(-1/2) \prod_{j=1}^{n/2-1} H_f(j/n). \end{aligned}$$

Now, note that $f(1/2)(P_f(-1/2))^2 = P(1/2)P(-1/2) = \frac{f(1/2)}{f(0)} H_f(1/2)$, and thus $P_f(-1/2) = f(0)^{-1/2} \sqrt{H_f(1/2)}$ (we chose the positive branch of the square root, since a reflective f is always positive). Hence, we obtain, for even $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} P_f(-j/n) = f(0)^{\frac{1-n}{2}} \sqrt{H_f(1/2)} \prod_{j=1}^{n/2-1} H_f(j/n).$$

Now

$$\sqrt{H_f(1/2)} = \exp\left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k^f ((-1)^k - 1)\right) = \exp\left(-\sum_{k \geq 1: k \text{ odd}} A_k^f\right),$$

and thus

$$\sqrt{H_f(1/2)} \prod_{j=1}^{n/2-1} H_f(j/n) = \exp\left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1: n \nmid k} A_k^f\right).$$

Observe that the formula is the same for both the even and odd cases. Thus, the proof is complete.

Theorem 7.3 (Multiplication formula for Eulerian reflective functions). *Let $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an Eulerian reflective function. Then, for $n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2$*

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} f(k) = n^{-\frac{r}{2}} \left(\frac{(2\pi)^r}{\lambda} \right)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1 : n \nmid k} A_k^h \right)$$

Proof. Since f is Eulerian reflective, there exists $r \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x)}{x^r} = \lambda > 0$. We now define $h(x)$ as

$$h(x) := \begin{cases} \frac{f(x)}{x^r} & x \neq 0 \\ \lambda & x = 0 \end{cases}$$

Then, for $n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2$,

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} h(k) = \prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} \frac{f(k)}{k^r} = \prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} f(k) \prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \Gamma(1 - j/n)^{-r}.$$

Using Gauss multiplication theorem for the Gamma function, we obtain

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \Gamma(1 - j/n)^{-r} = \frac{n^{r/2}}{(2\pi)^{\frac{n-1}{2}r}}$$

and since $h(x)$ is reflective, from the previous multiplication theorem we have

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} h(k) = \lambda^{\frac{1-n}{2}} \exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1 : n \nmid k} A_k^h \right).$$

Hence,

$$\frac{n^{r/2}}{(2\pi)^{\frac{n-1}{2}r}} \prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} f(k) = \lambda^{\frac{1-n}{2}} \exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1 : n \nmid k} A_k^h \right)$$

and finally

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} f(k) = n^{-\frac{r}{2}} \left(\frac{(2\pi)^r}{\lambda} \right)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1 : n \nmid k} A_k^h \right).$$

□

7.3 Non even Eulerian case

Proposition 7.4 (Multiplication formula for non-even Eulerian functions). *Let f be a non-even Eulerian function in the sense of Definition 5.4. Then, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2$,*

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{n-j/n} f(k) = n^{-r/2} \left(\frac{(2\pi)^r}{\lambda} \right)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \exp \left(\alpha \frac{1-n^2}{12n} - \frac{n}{2} \sum_{\substack{k \geq 1 \\ n \nmid k}} B_k \right).$$

Proof. The proof has the same argument used in Theorem 7.3. The Eulerian principal part gives again

$$n^{-r/2} \left(\frac{(2\pi)^r}{\lambda} \right)^{\frac{n-1}{2}}.$$

By Proposition 5.5, the only additional factor is

$$e^{\alpha(x^2-x)} H_h^B(x), \quad 0 < x < 1.$$

The quadratic contribution is

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{j^2}{n^2} - \frac{j}{n} \right) = -\frac{n^2-1}{12n},$$

where the factor 1/2 reflects the same pairing as in Theorem 7.3. Hence, it contributes

$$\exp \left(-\alpha \frac{n^2-1}{12n} \right).$$

Finally, applying Lemma 7.1 to

$$H_h^B(x) = \exp \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} B_k (\cos(2\pi kx) - 1) \right)$$

gives

$$\exp \left(-\frac{n}{2} \sum_{\substack{k \geq 1 \\ n|k}} B_k \right).$$

Multiplying the three contributions gives the correct formula. \square

8 On the reflection of q-Gamma

In this section, we use our framework to obtain an identity for the reflection of the q-Gamma function [1]. The asymptotic behavior of q-Gamma has been investigated by Moak and Zhang (see [6] [10]), while Banerjee and Wilkerson obtained an asymptotic reflection formula for $\Gamma_q(x)\Gamma_q(1-x)$ as $q \rightarrow 1^-$ (see [2, Corollary 4.2]). Our general reflection principle leads instead to an exact counterpart of this asymptotic reflection. We have not found this Eulerian decomposition with Fourier coefficients in the q-Gamma literature.

Proposition 8.1. *For $q \in (0, 1)$ and $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}$ we have*

$$\Gamma_q(1+x)\Gamma_q(1-x) = \frac{\pi(q^{|x|}-1)}{\ln(q)\sin(\pi|x|)} q^{\frac{x^2-|x|}{2}} H(x, q)$$

where

$$H(x, q) = \exp \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 - \cos(2\pi kx)}{k} \left(\coth \left(\frac{2\pi^2 k}{\ln q} \right) + 1 \right) \right).$$

Proof. Let

$$f(t) = 1 - q^t, \quad 0 < q < 1.$$

Then

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{1 - q^t}{t} = -\ln q,$$

and, moreover, we have $g'' \in L^1$. Thus f is a non-even Eulerian function with

$$\lambda = -\ln q.$$

Set

$$h(t) = \frac{1 - q^t}{t}, \quad g(t) = \ln h(t) = \ln(1 - q^t) - \ln t.$$

Then

$$\alpha = g'(0^+) = \frac{\ln q}{2}.$$

By Proposition 5.5, for $x \in (-1, 1) \setminus \{0\}$,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x (1 - q^k) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} (1 - q^k) = \frac{\pi(1 - q^{|x|})}{-\ln q \sin(\pi|x|)} q^{(x^2 - |x|)/2} H(x, q),$$

because $e^{\alpha(x^2 - |x|)} = q^{(x^2 - |x|)/2}$.

B_k coefficients

$$g''(t) = \frac{1}{t^2} - \frac{(\ln q)^2 q^t}{(1 - q^t)^2} = \frac{1}{t^2} - \frac{(\ln q)^2}{4 \sinh^2\left(\frac{t \ln q}{2}\right)}.$$

Hence

$$B_k = \frac{1}{\pi^2 k^2} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{1}{t^2} - \frac{(\ln q)^2}{4 \sinh^2\left(\frac{t \ln q}{2}\right)} \right) \cos(2\pi kt) dt.$$

We know that

$$\int_0^\infty \left(\frac{1}{t^2} - \frac{a^2}{4 \sinh^2(at/2)} \right) \cos(bt) dt = -\frac{\pi b}{2} \left(\coth\left(\frac{\pi b}{a}\right) + 1 \right), \quad a < 0, b > 0,$$

which follows from [5, 3.983(3)]. With $a = \ln q$ and $b = 2\pi k$, we obtain

$$\int_0^\infty g''(t) \cos(2\pi kt) dt = -\pi^2 k \left(\coth\left(\frac{2\pi^2 k}{\ln q}\right) + 1 \right).$$

Therefore

$$B_k = -\frac{1}{k} \left(\coth\left(\frac{2\pi^2 k}{\ln q}\right) + 1 \right),$$

and the expression for $H(x, q)$ follows. Finally, observe that both sides satisfy the same functional relation

$$F(x+1) = \frac{1 - q^{1+x}}{1 - q^{-x}} F(x),$$

hence the identity extends from the interval $(-1, 1)$ to every $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}$. \square

9 Other applications

9.1 The hyperbolic tangent

We now give a further Eulerian reflective example whose correction factor is explicit and quantitatively small. Let

$$f(x) = \tanh(x/2).$$

Then f has a polynomial zero at the origin. Indeed,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\tanh(x/2)}{x} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Thus $r = 1$ and $\lambda = 1/2$. We define

$$h(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tanh(x/2)}{x}, & x \neq 0, \\ \frac{1}{2}, & x = 0. \end{cases}$$

Then h is even, positive, continuous and differentiable in \mathbb{R} . Moreover, h is slowly varying, since for every fixed $x \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\frac{h(N+x)}{h(N)} = \frac{\tanh((N+x)/2)}{\tanh(N/2)} \frac{N}{N+x} \rightarrow 1 \quad (N \rightarrow +\infty).$$

Also, $g'' \in L^1(0, \infty)$. Thus, h belongs to the reflective class.

We now compute the Fourier coefficients of the correction factor. Since

$$g'(t) = \frac{1}{\sinh t} - \frac{1}{t},$$

we have

$$A_k^h = \frac{2}{\pi k} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{1}{\sinh t} - \frac{1}{t} \right) \sin(2\pi k t) dt.$$

Using the standard identities [5, 3.981 (1), p.509] and [5, 3.721 (1), p.423]

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{\sin(at)}{\sinh t} dt = \frac{\pi}{2} \tanh\left(\frac{\pi a}{2}\right), \quad \int_0^\infty \frac{\sin(at)}{t} dt = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad a > 0,$$

with $a = 2\pi k$, we obtain

$$\int_0^\infty \left(\frac{1}{\sinh t} - \frac{1}{t} \right) \sin(2\pi k t) dt = -\frac{\pi}{e^{2\pi^2 k} + 1}.$$

Therefore

$$A_k^h = -\frac{2}{k(e^{2\pi^2 k} + 1)}$$

and

$$H_h(x) = \exp \left(2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 - \cos(2\pi kx)}{k(e^{2\pi^2 k} + 1)} \right).$$

By the Eulerian reflection theorem, for every $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}$,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x \tanh(k/2) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} \tanh(k/2) = \frac{2\pi \tanh(x/2)}{\sin(\pi x)} \exp \left(2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 - \cos(2\pi kx)}{k(e^{2\pi^2 k} + 1)} \right).$$

By the multiplication theorem, we obtain instead

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{-j/n} \tanh(k/2) = \frac{(4\pi)^{\frac{n-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{n}} \exp \sum_{k \geq 1: n \nmid k} \frac{n}{k(e^{2\pi^2 k} + 1)}.$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2$.

Remark 9.1. Identities of this type are closely related to classical product formulas for Jacobi theta functions, in particular to Jacobi's triple product [4, §20.5(i), Eq. (20.5.9)]. The point of the example is rather structural: the formula is produced naturally by the Eulerian reflection theorem, and the Eulerian principal part captures almost the whole reflection.

Indeed, since $1 - \cos(2\pi kx) \leq 2$, one has

$$0 \leq \ln H_h(x) \leq 4 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k(e^{2\pi^2 k} + 1)} < 4 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-2\pi^2 k}}{k} = -4 \ln(1 - e^{-2\pi^2}).$$

Thus

$$0 \leq \ln H_h(x) < -4 \ln(1 - e^{-2\pi^2}) \approx 1.07 \cdot 10^{-8},$$

and therefore

$$\prod_{k=1}^x \tanh(k/2) \prod_{k=1}^{-x} \tanh(k/2) = \frac{2\pi \tanh(x/2)}{\sin(\pi x)} (1 + O(10^{-8})).$$

In this sense, the reflection is almost entirely governed by the Eulerian principal part.

9.2 Gauss-type multiplication for $\ln(1+t)$

Let $f(k) = \ln(1+k)$, and let

$$h(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{\ln(1+x)}{x}, & x \neq 0, \\ 1, & x = 0. \end{cases}$$

Using $g(x) = \ln h(x)$, we observe that $g'' \in L^1$, h is slow varying and $g'(0^+) = -\frac{1}{2}$. Thus, Proposition 7.4 gives, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq 2$,

$$\prod_{j=1}^{n-1} \prod_{k=1}^{-j/n} \ln(1+k) = \frac{(2\pi)^{\frac{n-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{n}} \exp\left(\frac{n^2-1}{24n} - \frac{n}{2} \sum_{\substack{k \geq 1 \\ n \nmid k}} B_k\right).$$

9.3 A case where $H(x) \equiv 1$

Proposition 9.2 (Inverse tangent reflection). *If m is a nonzero integer,*

$$\sum_{k=1}^x \arctan\left(\frac{2k^2}{m^2}\right) + \sum_{k=1}^{-x} \arctan\left(\frac{2k^2}{m^2}\right) = \arctan\left(\frac{2x^2}{m^2}\right)$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Hence,

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sum_{k=1}^{-j/n} \arctan\left(\frac{2k^2}{m^2}\right) \equiv 0$$

for all $n, m \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$.

Proof. **The reflection**

Consider a slightly more general function $f(k) = e^{\arctan(k^2/q^2)}$, for a real $q \neq 0$. Observe that $f(k)$ is reflective since it is product admissible, even, positive, slow varying, $\ln f \in C^2$ and $\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \arctan(x^2/q^2) \in L^1(0, \infty)$. Thus,

$$\prod_{k=1}^x e^{\arctan(k^2/q^2)} \prod_{k=1}^{-x} e^{\arctan(k^2/q^2)} = e^{\arctan(x^2/q^2)} H_f(x, q)$$

Taking the natural log on both sides gives

$$\sum_{k=1}^x \arctan\left(\frac{k^2}{q^2}\right) + \sum_{k=1}^{-x} \arctan\left(\frac{k^2}{q^2}\right) = \arctan\left(\frac{x^2}{q^2}\right) + \ln H_f(x, q)$$

Now

$$A_k^f = \frac{4q^2}{\pi k} \int_0^\infty \frac{t \sin(2\pi kt)}{q^4 + t^4} dt.$$

Using the standard identity [5, 3.727 (1), p.426]

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{\cos(bt)}{t^4 + q^4} dt = \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{2}q^3} e^{-\frac{qb}{\sqrt{2}}} \left(\cos \frac{qb}{\sqrt{2}} + \sin \frac{qb}{\sqrt{2}} \right), \quad b > 0,$$

and differentiating with respect to b , we obtain

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{t \sin(bt)}{t^4 + q^4} dt = \frac{\pi}{2q^2} e^{-\frac{qb}{\sqrt{2}}} \sin\left(\frac{qb}{\sqrt{2}}\right).$$

Therefore, with $b = 2\pi k$,

$$A_k^f = \frac{2}{k} e^{-\sqrt{2}\pi k q} \sin(\sqrt{2}\pi k q).$$

Observe using $q \rightarrow \frac{m}{\sqrt{2}}$, for $m \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$, then we have $A_k^f \equiv 0$ for each index k . Indeed, $\sin(\sqrt{2}\pi k q) = \sin(\pi k m) = 0$. Thus, also $H_f(x) \equiv 1$ for any real x . The first identity follows immediately.

The double summation Taking the logarithm of the multiplication formula for a reflective function, we have for $n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sum_{k=1}^{j/n} \ln f(k) = \frac{1-n}{2} \ln f(0) - \frac{n}{2} \sum_{k \geq 1 : n \nmid k} A_k^f.$$

Using $f(x) = e^{\arctan(2x^2/m^2)}$ we observe that $\ln(e^{\arctan(0)}) = \ln 1 = 0$ and $A_k^f \equiv 0$ for any natural index k when m is a nonzero integer. Hence, the claim follows for $n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2$. For $n = 1$ we have

$$\sum_{j=1}^0 \sum_{k=1}^{-1} f(k) = 0.$$

This completes the proof. □

Remark 9.3. The example of the inverse tangent shows that there exists a non-trivial function whose continuous reflected product has no correction factors at all. This raises the question whether there exists a real, nontrivial Eulerian reflective function for which $H(x) \equiv 1$. By "non-trivial" we mean a function $f(x)$ that cannot be globally decomposed into $x^r \cdot g(x)$ for some real r and whose continuous product is not telescopic in \mathbb{R} . If such a function were found, then we would have a continuous product with a pure Euler-type reflection formula.

10 Continuous Sums and Products as a Unified Language

As shown in the article, there is a direct connection between our framework and many elementary and special functions, such as

$$\prod_{k=1}^x k = \Gamma(x+1) \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{-1, -2, \dots\}$$

As a direct consequence,

$$\sum_{k=1}^x \frac{1}{k} = \psi(x+1) + \gamma \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{-1, -2, \dots\}.$$

Moreover, we have shown

$$\sin x = x \prod_{k=1}^{x/\pi} \left(1 - \frac{x}{\pi k}\right), \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \pi\mathbb{Z},$$

$$\prod_{k=1}^x (1 - q^k) = (1 - q)^x \Gamma_q(x + 1), \quad |q| < 1, x \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Müller and Schleicher have also proved

$$\sum_{k=1}^x k^a = \zeta(-a) - \zeta(-a, x + 1), \quad x \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{-1, -2, \dots\}, a \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{-1\}$$

(see [7, p.135, Corollary 14]). In this final section, we also discuss the connection between continuous products and the Barnes G function (see [3]).

Proposition 10.1. *For $x > -1$ we have*

$$\prod_{k=1}^x k^{x-k} = G(x + 1)$$

where $G(x)$ is the Barnes G function.

Proof. First, consider $\ln \prod_{k=1}^x k^k$. By Proposition 2.6, its expanded form is

$$\ln \prod_{k=1}^x k^k = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \ln \pi_f(x) + \sum_{k=1}^N [k \ln(k) - (k + x) \ln(k + x)]$$

where

$$\ln \pi_f(x) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=1}^x (k + N) \ln(k + N).$$

Since $k \geq 1$, $\ln(k + x)$ is well defined when $x > -1$. The asymptotic expansion for the inner term of the residual is

$$\begin{aligned} (N + k) \ln(N + k) &= N \ln(N) + (\ln N + 1)k + \frac{k^2}{2N} - \frac{k^3}{6N^2} + \dots \\ &= N \ln N + (\ln N + 1)k + O(N^{-1}) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the residual is

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=1}^x [N \ln(N) + (\ln N + 1)k] = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} Nx \ln N + (\ln N + 1) \frac{x(x + 1)}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^x O(N^{-1})$$

Since for finite x it holds $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=1}^x O(N^{-1}) = 0$, then finally

$$\prod_{k=1}^x k^k = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} N^{Nx} (eN)^{\frac{x(x+1)}{2}} \prod_{k=1}^N \frac{k^k}{(k+x)^{k+x}}.$$

Using the functional equation of the Barnes G , $G(z+1) = \Gamma(z)G(z)$, one has

$$\prod_{k=1}^N (k+x)^k = \frac{\Gamma(N+x+1)^N G(x+1)}{G(N+x+1)}.$$

Consequently,

$$\prod_{k=1}^N \frac{k^k}{(k+x)^{k+x}} = \frac{\Gamma(1+x)^x}{G(1+x)} \frac{\Gamma(N+1)^N G(N+x+1)}{\Gamma(N+x+1)^{N+x} G(N+1)}.$$

By Stirling's formula and the standard asymptotic expansion of the Barnes function, the second factor is asymptotic to $N^{-Nx} (eN)^{-x(x+1)/2}$. Therefore

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} N^{Nx} (eN)^{x(x+1)/2} \prod_{k=1}^N \frac{k^k}{(k+x)^{k+x}} = \frac{\Gamma(1+x)^x}{G(1+x)}.$$

Since

$$\prod_{k=1}^x k^k = \frac{\Gamma(x+1)^x}{G(x+1)} = \frac{\prod_{k=1}^x k^x}{G(x+1)},$$

then

$$\prod_{k=1}^x k^{k-x} = \frac{1}{G(x+1)},$$

and the claim follows. \square

11 Further directions

Natural continuations include:

- Trying to extend the reflection scheme to non-slow varying functions.
- Extending the reflection scheme to complex domains, clarifying analytic continuation, holomorphy, and singularity structure.
- Finding a non-trivial Eulerian reflective function with $H(x) \equiv 1$; we leave this question as an open problem.

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Acknowledgements

I warmly thank Professor Alessandro Iacopetti for his support and for the helpful advice he gave me during the preparation of this manuscript.

I also thank Markus Müller and Dierk Schleicher for their encouraging comments on an earlier version of this work.